

Managing Emotional Intelligence for Effective Leadership in Organization

Dr. Seema Singh¹, Ms. Aditi²

¹Assistant Professor, ²BBA (Scholar)

^{1,2}Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Agra, Uttar Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Leadership is described as the heart of every organization and it is a process of leading followers/team. To get better outcome from the employees and to achieve the organizational goals, the leader should be able to understand the pulse of the employees and his or her own. This research study is to understand how the employees Emotional Intelligence can be enhanced for developing effective leadership skills within them. Emotional intelligence has become increasingly popular as a measure for identifying potentially effective leaders, as a tool for developing effective leadership skills. The aim of the present paper was to explore the relationship between emotional intelligence and effective leadership. There are numerous definitions of such leadership that have come to light however these definitions have always been debatable. Most scholars agree that the concept of leadership does not ascribe to one specific definition however, provided the following definition of leadership in his landmark publication, leadership: "Leaders inducing followers to act for certain goals that represent the values and the motivations – the wants and needs, the aspirations and expectations – of both leaders and followers

Emotional intelligence correlated with several components transformational leadership suggesting that it may be an important components of effective leadership in particular emotional intelligence leader's monitors and respond to subordinates and make them feel at work.

KEYWORDS: Emotional intelligence, effectiveness, leadership

INTRODUCTION

Interpersonal skills have become more integral to effective leadership and Emotional Intelligence (also known as Emotional Quotient) is one of the hot topics among business leaders and HR professionals lately. Emotional Intelligence (EI) has had a huge impact on management since Daniel Goleman (1995) published his book popular book on EI for a wider audience. From fairly humble beginnings, EI has come into its own as one of the most popular psychological concepts of the last decade. EI has been used by some as an umbrella term that comprises elements such as 'soft skills', 'people skills', and a general ability to cope with life's demands. In other words 'Emotional intelligence gives you a competitive edge'. It has been argued around the world that having great intellectual abilities may make you a superb fiscal analyst or legal scholar, but a highly developed emotional intelligence will make you a candidate for CEO or a brilliant trial lawyer" as it enhance the hidden leader with in you . Leadership is a desirable quality, so it comes as no surprise that much study has been done in attempts to identify the key elements of an effective leader. Much of that study has focused on the specific character, personality, or behavioural traits that most effective leaders have in common. The evidence is mixed on whether traits or personality can predict leadership potential. In the following section, we will examine some of the commonly identified leadership traits along with some of the leadership styles individuals' display.

Objectives

The main objective of this research paper are as follows:-

1. To study the conceptual framework of emotional intelligence.
2. To study the factors effecting the emotional intelligence and leadership.
3. To study the relationship between the emotional intelligence and leadership.
4. To study the emotional intelligence and its effects in formulating effective leaders.
5. To develop a relationship model of emotional intelligence and leadership.

Emotional intelligence and its relevance

Emotional intelligence or EI is the ability to understand and manage your own emotions, and those of the people around you. People with a high degree of emotional intelligence know what they're feeling, what their emotions mean, and how these emotions can affect other people.

Emotional intelligence (EI), emotional leadership (EL), emotional quotient (EQ) and emotional intelligence quotient (EIQ), is the capability of individuals to recognize their own emotions and those of others, discern between different feelings and label them appropriately, use emotional information to guide thinking and behaviour or adjust emotions to adapt to environments or achieve one's goals.

How to cite this paper: Dr. Seema Singh | Ms. Aditi "Managing Emotional Intelligence for Effective Leadership in Organization"

Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-6, October 2019, pp.515-519, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23629.pdf>

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

For leaders, having emotional intelligence is essential for success. After all, who is more likely to succeed – a leader who shouts at his team when he's under stress, or a leader who stays in control, and calmly assesses the situation.

You may be thinking of an excelling leaders as someone who has a calm assuring demeanour and who is in control no matter what the situation. You may also think of someone who has complete trust in all around them; a compassionate listener, always speaking kindly and with clarity; is approachable and always seems to make the right informed decisions.

Effectively, these are all attributes of someone who has high levels of Emotional Intelligence. Referencing Salovey above: the leader is controlling his/her own emotions as well as those of the team to perform excelling results. It is, therefore an extremely important subject – Emotional Intelligence theory and Leadership have a deep embedded relationship that should not be underestimated or overlooked.

It has been observed that transformational behaviours on the part of leaders promote empowering cultural norms, high levels of subordinate motivation, commitment to quality, and enhanced productivity. It was seen that empowering cultural norms of organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) promotes constructive and achievement-oriented behaviour by members. Such norms are associated with basic values and shared assumptions emphasizing the significance of organizational members' roles and collaboration through motivation rather than by competition. Motivation in this context is the extrinsically stimulated "extra effort" on the part of subordinates inspired by transformational leaders. Transformational leaders enhance the OCB of followers through motivation.

Studies have shown that people with high EI have greater mental health, job performance, and leadership skills although no causal relationships have been shown and such findings are likely to be attributable to general

4 Pillars of emotional intelligence

Daniel Goleman, (2002), A psychologist who helped make the idea of EI popular, presented the concept of Emotional Intelligence as being encapsulated by four elements:

- Self-Awareness
- Self-Management.
- Social skills.
- Social Awareness

intelligence and specific personality traits rather than emotional intelligence as a construct. For example, Gleeman indicated that EI accounted for 67% of the abilities deemed necessary for superior performance in leaders, and mattered twice as much as technical expertise or IQ.^[12] Other research finds that the effect of EI on leadership and managerial performance is non-significant when ability and personality are controlled, and that general intelligence correlates very closely with leadership. Markers of EI and methods of developing it have become more widely coveted in the past decade. In addition, studies have begun to provide evidence to help characterize the neural mechanisms of emotional intelligence.

Emotional intelligence also reflects abilities to join intelligence, empathy and emotions to enhance thought and understanding of interpersonal dynamics. However, substantial disagreement exists regarding the definition of EI, with respect to both terminology and operationalization's.

Currently, there are three main models of EI:

1. Ability model
2. Mixed model (usually subsumed under trait EI)
3. Trait model

Emotional intelligence is about having the ability to understand and manage the emotions of yourself and also those around you. Remember, the objective of a leader is to complete the task successfully, keep the team together and manage the team on an individual basis to ensure everyone is happy and playing to their strengths as Leadership is a matter of intelligence, trustworthiness, humaneness, courage, and discipline ... Reliance on intelligence alone results in rebelliousness. Exercise of humaneness alone results in weakness. Fixation on trust results in folly. Dependence on the strength of courage results in violence. Excessive discipline and sternness in command result in cruelty. When one has all five virtues together, each appropriate to its function, then one can be a leader.

The theory is simple – The more that you, as a leader, are in control and manage each of these elements, the higher your emotional intelligence.

1. Self-awareness

If you're self-aware, you always know how you feel, and you know how your emotions and your actions can affect the people around you. Being self-aware when you're in a leadership position also means having a clear picture of your **strengths and weaknesses, and it means behaving with humility.**

So, what can you do to improve your self-awareness?

- **Keep a journal** – Journals help you improve your self-awareness. If you spend just a few minutes each day writing down your thoughts, this can move you to a higher degree of self-awareness.
- **Slow down** – When you experience anger or other strong emotions, slow down to examine why. Remember, no matter what the situation, you can always choose how you react to it.

2. Self-Management

The second element of Goleman's Emotional Intelligence theory: – Through being in control of what you say and do, whilst rejecting the temptation to make rushed decisions, you can be in charge of your actions and therefore reducing the chance of compromising your values. Other aspects to nurture in this element are to show and actively apply conscientiousness, trustworthiness, Leading and adapting to change, complete drive to succeed and the initiative to think fast and act creatively and innovatively to solve problems.

Self-management skills are those characteristics that help an employee to feel and be more productive in the workplace. Such skills as problem solving, resisting stress, communicating clearly, **managing** time, strengthening memory, and exercising often are all key examples of **self-management** skills.

3. Social Awareness

The third element of Emotional Intelligence Theory: Social awareness is the ability for a Leader to understand the emotions of the team members around them and to get a good comprehension of their emotional makeup. The ability to treat people according to these emotional reactions is vital. This area is linked to empathy: The ability to understand and see things in other peoples view points, expertise in building and retaining talent, valuing diversity and appreciating the organisational goals. In essence this part of emotional intelligence then, is about understanding and being truly in touch with the complete demands of the environment and acting to suit those conditions.

Self-Awareness is having a clear perception of your personality, including strengths, weaknesses, thoughts, beliefs, motivation, and emotions. **Self-awareness** allows you to understand other people, how they perceive you, your attitude and your responses to them in the moment.

4. Social skills

The final element from Goleman's emotional intelligence theory, which links Leadership and Emotional Intelligence together: Leaders with good Social Skills are often very good communicators. Leaders who are good in this discipline are also good at conflict resolution and communicating the vision to team members, enlightening them and creating motivation and inspiration throughout the team. They are experts at getting their team to support them and also believe in their leadership. They set the example, for others to follow by demonstrating the acceptable behaviours and values.

Adapted from Mayer & Salovey (1997)

So, how can you build social skills?

- **Learn conflict resolution** – Leaders must know how to resolve conflicts between their team members, customers, or vendors. Learning **conflict resolution** skills is vital if you want to succeed.
- **Improve your communication skills** – How well do you communicate? Our **communication quiz** will help you answer this question, and it will give useful feedback on what you can do to improve.
- **Learn how to praise others** – As a leader, you can inspire the loyalty of your team simply by **giving praise**.

RECOMMENDED MODEL OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND EFFECTIVE LEADERSHIP

Based on the various literature surveys, it is established that developing a model of EI with the important components as self-awareness, self-management and self-confident have co-relation with effective leadership traits such as self-perception, decision making power, emotional characters & stress management. It is thereby to inform that managers with high Emotional intelligence are competent leaders and will be able to influence more of his followers with his individual personality and motivate them very well to achieve once goals for the organization and individual. Also with enhanced Emotional intelligence competency the self-management will be more pronounced, and he/she can give individualized consideration to his followers. The model is pictorial representation of the thoughts which will present a new methodology of effective leaders.

RELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND EFFECTIVE LEADERSHIP

The relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Effectiveness Within the research literature, there is a wealth of evidence that suggests that effective leadership is significantly correlated with emotional intelligence.

“Leadership is a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal”. Hollander (1978) espoused that in the system theory, leadership was a process of mutual influence between leaders and followers which vacillates among leaders, followers, and the situation at hand. Mayer and Salovey (1997), in their definition of emotional intelligence (EI), stated that EI is “the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth”.

On the other hand, transformational leadership functions through the notions of motivating and stimulating the co-workers in order to create a completely different perspective

on the organizational objectives and foster an atmosphere where the employees are motivated to achieve higher levels of capability while inspiring the employees to put team interests before personal interests. Thus, transformational leadership rests on four basic pillars: intellectual incentive, edified influence, inspirational motivation, and consideration for each individual employee.

The Centre for Creative Leadership (2001) findings suggested that higher levels of emotional intelligence were correlated with better performance in nine key areas: participative management; putting people at ease; balance between personal life and work; straightforwardness and composure; building and mending relationships; doing whatever it takes; decisiveness; confronting problem employees; and change management. The Centre for Creative Leadership (2001) study concluded that “co-workers seemed to appreciate managers’ ability to control their emotions and leaders are more likely to be seen as participative, composed, and balanced” (p. 4). Similarly, Dasborough and Ashkanasy’s (2003) qualitative study revealed that leaders who provided encouragement to their employees were perceived by employees to be the most

effective. Previous research studies have suggested the emotional intelligence has little to no effect on leadership effectiveness (Antonakis, 2003; Antonakis, Ashkanasy, & Dasborough, 2009; Collins, 2001; Schulte, Ree, & Corretta, 2004; Waterhouse, 2006).

The most effective leaders are all alike in one crucial way: they all have a high degree of what has come to be known as emotional intelligence. It's not that IQ and technical skills are irrelevant. They do matter, but...they are the entry-level requirements for executive positions. My research, along with other recent studies, clearly shows that emotional intelligence is the sine qua non of leadership. Without it, a person can have the best training in the world, an incisive, analytical mind, and an endless supply of smart ideas, but he still won't make a great leader.

Suggestion for better relationship between employer and employee for effective leadership

- Highly emotionally intelligent individuals are perceived more positively by others – Other individuals perceive those with high EI to be more pleasant, socially skilled and empathic to be around.
- Better social relations during work performance and in negotiations.
- For a Better psychological well-being.
- Allows for self-compassion.
- Understand your value.
- Be countable for your action.
- Turn negative situation into positive.
- Learn how to praise others.
- Re- examine why you are a leader and keep up grading your standards .

Conclusion

There are sufficient evidence to support the hypothesis that the leaders with higher emotional intelligence are effective leaders .there are significant relationship between selected components of effective leadership and emotional intelligence .those leaders who consider themselves to motivate and inspire subordinate to work towards the common goal , reported that they monitored and manage emotions and both within themselves and others. The

components “charisma” defines inspiration and motive to inspire their sub ordinate to work towards their common goal. The present result suggest that one of the underlying competencies of these skills may be the ability to monitor emotions both within one and others. In addition inspire the leaders to be positive and also develop the ability to manage emotions for better management and better result.

There is a significant positive correlation between the cognitive reward components of effective leadership and ability to manage one and other emotions.it will enhance ones confidence and will help to achieve the future goals of an organization.

“A **leader** is best when people barely know he exists, when his work is done, his aim fulfilled, they will say: we did it ourselves.” ~ Lao Tzu.

Reference

[1] Wikipedia .com (Google , scholar).

[2] Burns JM. New York: Harper and Row; 1978. Leadership. [Google Scholar]

[3] Salovey P, Mayer J. Emotional intelligence. *Imagin Cogn Pers.* 1990; 9:185–211. [Google Scholar]

[4] Bardzill P, Slaski M. Emotional intelligence: Fundamental competencies for enhanced service provision. *Manag Serv Qual.* 2003; 13:97–104. [Google Scholar]

[5] Welch J. The best teams are emotionally literate. *Ind Commer Train.* 2003; 35:168–71. [Google Scholar]

[6] Turner L. Emotional Intelligence-our intangible assets. *Chart Account J N Z.* 2004;83:29–31.[Google Scholar]

[7] Goleman , R (1997), what is a leader? Harvrad business review. Vol76, pp 96-104.

[8] Lowe, K. B and Kroeck, K. G (1996), “Effectiveness Corelates of Transformational and Trsational Leadersip: A Metal Analytics Review”, *Leadership Quartly*, Vol 7, Pp 385-426.